

REPORT

A.2.2.6: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for terpenes

As part of WP2 task 2.2, BiometCAP partners have demonstrated the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in Task 2.1 (specifically in A2.1.4) using the following validated methods: gas chromatography, spectroscopy and spectrometry analytical systems. The validation exercise is shown on the map below:

NPL and RISE will each validate the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for 2 terpenes (e.g. α -pinene, β -pinene, 3-carene, limonene, p-cymene) using a gas chromatography mass spectrometry flame ionization detector with thermal desorption (TD-GC/MS/FID) (RISE) or without thermal desorption (GC/MS/FID) (NPL). NPL and RISE will use the static standards produced in A1.1.2. A short-written report will be produced by NPL and RISE.

The two reports are gathered in this document.

REPORT

A2.2.6: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for three terpenes using GC-MS/FID with the static standards produced in A1.1.2.

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1: Introduction

The EURAMET project “BiometCAP” has developed a performance assessment protocol for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. This report describes the validation of analytical methods for determining the amount fraction of three terpenes, namely d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene, in samples of synthetic biomethane using GC-MS/FID, according to the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4.

The methods were validated using dynamic standards produced using a thermal mass flow controller system, referred to herein as the “MFC dynamic system”. The dynamic standards were generated by diluting a static standard (D115836) with N 6.0 purity grade methane gas, using the MFC dynamic system with calculated blend ratios to achieve the desired amount fractions. The dynamic system was validated using a static “check standard” (D618323). The static standards used herein were prepared gravimetrically and validated against NPL primary reference materials (NPL PRMs).

The following performance criteria were evaluated as part of this report:

- Linearity;
- Selectivity;
- Trueness;
- Precision; and
- Limit-of-detection and limit of quantification.

The general procedure for evaluating the performance of each analytical method is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 – Overview of performance evaluation process.

Step	Phase	Description	Plan										
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	<p>d-limonene, α-pinene, and 3-carene will be measured at 0.005 to 3.367 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$. The criteria and target values are as below:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Criteria</td> <td>Target value</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)</td> <td>0.005 - 3.367</td> </tr> <tr> <td>R² over working range</td> <td>> 0.995</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LOD (nmol mol⁻¹)</td> <td>< 30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LOQ (nmol mol⁻¹)</td> <td>< 100</td> </tr> </table>	Criteria	Target value	Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.005 - 3.367	R ² over working range	> 0.995	LOD (nmol mol ⁻¹)	< 30	LOQ (nmol mol ⁻¹)	< 100
Criteria	Target value												
Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.005 - 3.367												
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			<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Trueness (%)</td> <td>6.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Repeatability (%)</td> <td>6.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Intermediate precision (%)</td> <td>6.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Expanded uncertainty (%)</td> <td>6.00</td> </tr> </table>	Trueness (%)	6.00	Repeatability (%)	6.00	Intermediate precision (%)	6.00	Expanded uncertainty (%)	6.00
Trueness (%)	6.00										
Repeatability (%)	6.00										
Intermediate precision (%)	6.00										
Expanded uncertainty (%)	6.00										
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The instrument should show a linear response over the range of interest.								
3	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Gravimetric composition and uncertainties calculated using NPL software GravCalc2.								
4	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	One dilution standard (D115836), one check standard (D618323) and one interference standard (D223095).								
5	Experimental	Perform a multi-point calibration experiment by collecting instrument response data for measurements of the reference gas mixtures designed and produced in accordance with step 4. The entire experiment should be conducted within a time period equivalent to that between routine calibrations.	Dilution of D115836 with N 6.0 methane up to a dilution factor of 600 to produce a calibration curve which is validated with the check standard to assess working range, linearity, and trueness. The curve is repeated on three days over two weeks to assess precision.								

2: Analytical method

The GC-MS/FID can be used to detect and identify gaseous components in biomethane samples. The GC uses helium carrier gas, and separation is achieved through a 75 m length, 0.53 mm inner diameter DB-624 fused silica column. The method used is 12 minutes long, to allow for complete separation of methane and the three terpenes of interest (d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene).

Components are identified and quantified by the flame ionisation detector (FID) or the quadrupole mass spectrometer (MS) detector. The FID operates by burning the components in a hydrogen flame and measuring the change in electrical current across the detector, allowing the separate components to be quantified. The MS operates in electron impact (EI) mode with an ionisation energy of 70 eV and a quadrupole scan range of 10-400 amu. The quadrupole detector operates by passing the ionised analytes through a vacuum chamber with four charged rods; wherein the rods generate an electrical field which directs ions with a

specified mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) towards the detector, allowing for accurate identification and quantification of the individual components *via* their parent ions' m/z and fragmentation patterns.

Dynamic gas standards were generated using the MFC dynamic system which was connected to the GC-MS-FID via a SilcoNert® 2000 coated stainless steel tubing, with a bypass system to achieve a consistent flow rate of 25 ml min^{-1} for all measurements (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1 – MFC dynamic dilution system used in this study.

3: Reference standards

Two NPL PRMs were prepared in accordance with ISO 614201 and validated using a direct comparison based on ISO 6143. The standards were prepared in 10 litre Air Liquide “Megalife” passivated cylinders. Previously developed GC-MS/FID methods were used for the validation of these PRMs. The amount fractions of the terpenes were selected to facilitate dynamic dilution over 0.01 to $9 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ of total terpenes (*Table 2*).

Table 2 – Static PRMs used in this study and their gravimetric compositions.

Component	Amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	
	D115836	D618323
d-limonene	3.280	2.040
α -pinene	3.367	2.070
3-carene	3.123	2.020
Total terpenes	9.9769	6.130
Methane	Balance	Balance

4: Linearity

4.1: Calibration curves

Calibration curves for the quantification of d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene in synthetic biomethane using FID and MS detectors were generated by blending D115836 with N 6.0 purity grade methane using the MFC dynamic dilution system developed by NPL. The calibration curves were generated using NPL software XLGenline, which provides a best fit of the data considering the uncertainties associated with the Y and X values. At least four points for each curve were generated to obtain an amount fraction range of each terpene from 0.005 to 3.367 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, corresponding to 0.016 to 9.769 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ total terpenes, as summarised in Table 3. A minimum of five repeat runs for each point were averaged when processing the data.

Table 3 – Calculated amount fractions generated by diluting standard D115836 with N 6.0 purity grade methane to generate the calibration curves.

Dilution factor	d-limonene ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	α -pinene ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	3-carene ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	Total terpenes ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)
1.0	3.280	3.367	3.123	9.769
1.6	2.050	2.104	1.952	6.106
5	0.656	0.673	0.625	1.954
50	0.066	0.067	0.063	0.195
600	0.005	0.006	0.005	0.016

For the FID detector, calibration curves were calculated for four amount fractions between 0.066 to 3.280 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ d-limonene, 0.067 to 3.367 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ α -pinene, and 0.063 to 3.123 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ 3-carene. Visual inspection of the calibration curves, shown in Figures 2-4, indicate that the response for the FID detector was linear over the amount fraction ranges studied. The calculated correlation coefficients suggest that the linear regressions fit the data well.

Figure 2 – d-limonene FID calibration curve from 0.066 to 3.28 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ d-limonene. Black points indicate calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, cyan point indicates static check standard, and the blue line indicates the calibration curve. An R^2 value of 0.999 is considered acceptable.

Figure 3 – α -pinene calibration curve from 0.067 to 3.36 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ α -pinene. Black points indicate calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, cyan point indicates static check standard, and the blue line indicates the calibration curve. An R^2 value of 0.9985 is considered acceptable.

3-carene FID 02/07/2024

Figure 4 – 3-carene calibration curve from 0.062 to 3.12 µmol mol⁻¹ 3-carene. Black points indicate calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, cyan point indicates static check standard, and the blue line indicates the calibration curve. An R² value of 0.9983 is considered acceptable.

For the MS detector, calibration curves were calculated for five amount fractions between 0.005 to 3.280 µmol mol⁻¹ d-limonene, 0.006 to 3.367 µmol mol⁻¹ α-pinene, and 0.005 to 3.123 µmol mol⁻¹ 3-carene. Visual inspection of the calibration curves shown in Figures 5-7 indicate that the response for the MS detector was second-order over the amount fraction ranges studied. The calculated correlation coefficients suggest that the linear regressions fit the data well.

Figure 5 – d-limonene MS calibration curve from 0.006 to 3.28 µmol mol⁻¹ d-limonene. Black points indicate calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, cyan point indicates static check standard, and the red line indicates the calibration curve. An R^2 value of 0.9977 is considered acceptable.

α -pinene SIM 02/07/2024

Figure 6 – α -pinene MS calibration curve from 0.006 to 3.36 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ α -pinene. Black points indicate calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, cyan point indicates static check standard, and the red line indicates the calibration curve. An R^2 value of 0.9989 is considered acceptable.

Figure 7 – 3-carene MS calibration curve from 0.005 to 3.12 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ 3-carene. Black points indicate calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, cyan point indicates static check standard, and the red line indicates the calibration curve. An R^2 value of 0.9999 is considered acceptable.

4.2: Inspection of residuals

The residual peak areas for each calibration curve were calculated and plotted to inspect if any trends were visible for each of the six described regression models. A random distribution of residuals with no clear trend indicates that the regression model is valid over the working range.

Figure 8- Plot of residual peak areas from linear regression of d-limonene FID data. No trend was visible.

Figure 9 – Plot of residual peak areas from linear regression of α -pinene FID data. No trend was visible.

3-carene FID residuals 02/07/2024

Figure 10 – Plot of residual peak areas from linear regression of 3-carene FID data. No trend was visible.

d-limonene SIM residuals 02/07/2024

Figure 11 - Plot of residual peak areas from linear regression of d-limonene MS data. No trend was visible.

Figure 12 - Plot of residual peak areas from linear regression of α -pinene MS data. No trend was visible.

Figure 13 - Plot of residual peak areas from linear regression of 3-carene MS data. No trend was visible.

The linear regression models described for the quantification of d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene in synthetic biomethane using the FID detector demonstrate a linear working range of 0.066 to 3.280 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ d-limonene, 0.067 to 3.367 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ α -pinene, and 0.063 to 3.123 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ 3-carene. The distribution of residual peak areas is random and confirms the linearity of the model over the working range.

The linear regression models for the quantification of d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene in synthetic biomethane using the MS detector demonstrates a second order fit over the range of 0.005 to 3.280 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ d-limonene, 0.006 to 3.367 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ α -pinene, and 0.005 to 3.123 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ 3-carene. Due to the non-linearity of the MS detector's response, it is important to calibrate over the entire range of interest to determine that the calibration curve is fit for purpose.

5: Trueness

The calculated amount fraction of the three terpenes in the check standard using the calibration curve was compared to the gravimetric value of the PRM according to Equation 1.

$$\Delta_m = |c_m - c_{ref}| \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where:

Δ_m = the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value;

c_m = the mean measured value; and

c_{ref} = the gravimetric standard reference value.

The expanded uncertainty of the difference was determined by the quadrature sum of the uncertainties of the reference value and the measurement results according to Equation 2.

$$U_{\Delta} = 2 \sqrt{u_m^2 + u_{ref}^2} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where:

U_{Δ} = the expanded uncertainty of the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value ($k = 2$);

u_m = the uncertainty of the mean measured value ($k = 1$); and

u_{ref} = the uncertainty of the reference value ($k = 1$).

The expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainty corresponds to a confidence interval of 95%.

If the expanded uncertainty of the difference is inferior to the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value, the difference is considered significant (highlighted red).

The following tables provide an overview of the trueness of the calibration curve as measured against the static reference standard D618323. The calculated amount fraction is an average of 5 repeated measurements.

Table 4 – Summary of trueness analysis for the FID detector.

D618323	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.040	2.070	2.020
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.005	0.002	0.015
Mean measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.059	2.128	2.022
Uncertainty of measured value u_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.029	0.018	0.046
Relative difference (%)	0.94	2.80	0.123
Relative trueness uncertainty U_{Δ} (%)	2.91	1.77	4.74

Using the FID detector, the calculated d-limonene and 3-carene amount fractions agreed with the gravimetric amount fractions within the expanded uncertainty. The α -pinene measurement was found to have a bias larger than the measurement uncertainty compared to the gravimetric amount fraction (shown in red in Table 4).

Table 5 – Summary of trueness analysis for the MS detector.

D618323	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.040	2.070	2.020
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.005	0.002	0.015
Mean measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.139	2.19	1.97
Uncertainty of measured value u_m	0.027	0.066	0.035
Relative difference (%)	4.85	5.800	-3.51
Relative trueness uncertainty U_{Δ} (%)	2.65	6.37	3.78

Using the MS detector, the calculated α -pinene and 3-carene amount fractions agreed with the gravimetric amount fractions within the expanded uncertainty. The d-limonene

measurement was found to have a bias larger than the measurement uncertainty compared to the gravimetric amount fraction (shown in red in Table 5).

6: Precision

6.1: Repeatability

Measurement precision was split into repeatability and intermediate precision to distinguish the uncertainty contribution linked to the instrument (repeatability) and the uncertainty contribution due to day-to-day effects (intermediate precision).

The repeatability of the measurement method was determined by seven repeat measurements of the check standard (D618323). The repeatability was estimated as the maximum relative standard deviation obtained from the measurements.

Table 6 – Repeatability of FID detector measuring D618323.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.040	2.070	2.020
RSD (%)	0.85	0.41	1.07

Table 7 – Repeatability of MS detector measuring D618323.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.040	2.070	2.020
RSD (%)	0.44	0.66	0.72

Repeatability values of less than 6% are considered acceptable.

6.2 Within-lab reproducibility (intermediate precision)

The dynamic system was used to generate calibration curves on three separate dates, and the amount fraction of the three terpenes in the check standard were calculated through at least 5 repeats on each day. The calculated amount fractions and relative standard deviations for the FID detector and MS detector are presented in Tables 8 and 9 respectively.

Table 8 – Summary of within-lab reproducibility analysis for the FID detector.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.040	2.070	2.020
Gravimetric uncertainty ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.005	0.002	0.015
02/07/2024 Measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.059	2.128	2.022
02/07/2024 Uncertainty of measured value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.029	0.018	0.046
01/07/2024 Measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.24	2.125	2.007
01/07/2024 Uncertainty of measured value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.035	0.014	0.390
23/07/2024 Measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.031	2.120	2.107
23/07/2024 Uncertainty of measured value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.024	0.010	0.027
Mean measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.095	2.124	2.045
Mean measured amount fraction SD ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.0017	0.00404	0.0088
Mean measured amount fraction RSD (%)	5.38	0.19	0.436

Reproducibility values of below 6% are considered acceptable. The reproducibility for d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene using the FID is below 6%, meaning that the method is suitable for measurement of these analytes. The reproducibility for d-limonene is noticeably larger than for the other terpenes measured; however, this can be improved by excluding d-limonene amount fraction from 01/07/2024, which appears to be an outlier.

Table 9 - Summary of within-lab reproducibility analysis for the MS detector.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.040	2.070	2.020
Gravimetric uncertainty ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.005	0.002	0.015
02/07/2024 Measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.100	2.150	1.97
02/07/2024 Uncertainty of measured value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.027	0.066	0.035
01/07/2024 Measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.044	2.081	2.086
01/07/2024 Uncertainty of measured value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.074	0.569	0.063
23/07/2024 Measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.022	1.981	2.044
23/07/2024 Uncertainty of measured value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.056	0.050	0.037
Mean measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	2.055	2.074	2.067
Mean measured amount fraction SD ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.040	0.080	0.059
Mean measured amount fraction RSD (%)	1.96	4.87	2.902

The data for d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene using the MS detector are less reproducible than the FID detector, but still within the 6% performance requirement.

7: Limit of detection and quantification

The limit of quantification (LOQ) is the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently determined using an analytical method, whereas the limit of detection refers to the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently detected. The LOQ and LODs for the described analytical methods were evaluated using the signal-to-noise approach, wherein the signal height of a low amount fraction sample is compared to the instrument baseline. A signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1 is considered acceptable for evaluating the LOQ, and a ratio of 3 is acceptable for evaluating the LOD, as described in Equation 3.

$$LOQ/LOD = x \left(\frac{S}{N} \right) C \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Where:

x = 3 when determining LOD, 10 when determining LOQ;

S = signal height;

N = noise height; and

C = gravimetric amount fraction of the component.

The results of the LOD and LOQ evaluations for the FID and MS detectors are presented in Tables 10 and 11.

Table 10 – Summary of LOQ and LOD analysis for FID detector.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
LOD (nmol mol ⁻¹)	12	13	12
LOQ (nmol mol ⁻¹)	40	42	37

Table 11 – Summary of LOQ and LOD analysis for MS detector.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
LOD (nmol mol ⁻¹)	7	8	7
LOQ (nmol mol ⁻¹)	24	27	24

8: Interferences/selectivity

To evaluate selectivity, a mixture containing five siloxanes, three terpenes, and two BTEX was run. This mixture was prepared in A1.2.2 and the composition (*Table 12*) was chosen to cover the common impurities found in biomethane.

Table 12 – Gravimetric composition of the biomethane mixture D223095 used for interference testing.

Component	Amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)
α -pinene	3.290
d-limonene	3.147
3-carene	2.923
Benzene	9.997
Toluene	10.002
L2 siloxane	0.084
L3 siloxane	0.056
D3 siloxane	0.056
D4 siloxane	0.042
D5 siloxane	0.033
Hexane	1.071
Methane	Balance

The chromatograms in Figures 14 and 15 show good separation of the three terpenes and the interferent compounds for both methods tested.

Figure 14 – FID chromatogram of standard D223095 used for interference testing. Good separation between the three terpenes of interest and the interferents is observed.

Figure 15 – MS chromatogram of standard D223095 used for interference testing. Good separation between the three terpenes of interest and the interferents is observed.

9: Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty budget for each analytical method was calculated according to Equation 4.

$$U = k \sqrt{u_r^2 + u_{day}^2 + \Delta_m^2} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where:

- U = the expanded uncertainty of the analytical method;
- k = the coverage factor ($k = 2$ for 95% confidence level);
- u_r = the relative uncertainty due to measurement repeatability;
- u_{day} = the relative uncertainty due to day-to-day variations (within-lab reproducibility); and
- Δ_m = the bias of the analytical method.

The resulting uncertainty budgets for the quantification of terpenes in biomethane using GC-MS and GC-FID are summarised in Tables 13 and 14.

Table 13 – Summary of uncertainty budget for GC-FID analytical method.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Repeatability u_r (%)	0.85	0.41	1.07
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	5.38	0.19	0.44
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	0.94	2.80	0.12
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	11.04	5.67	2.32

An expanded uncertainty of less than 6% is considered acceptable for the analysis of terpenes in biomethane. As such, the uncertainty budgets calculated for the α-pinene and 3-carene using FID is considered valid. The large uncertainty for d-limonene using the FID detector is due to the poor reproducibility introduced by the results of 01/07/2024 (see Section 8, Table 10). Excluding the outlying data would give a reproducibility of 1.45% and an expanded uncertainty of 3.85% for d-limonene using the FID detector, which would be considered acceptable.

Table 14 - Summary of uncertainty budget for GC-MS analytical method.

	d-limonene	α-pinene	3-carene
Repeatability u_r (%)	0.44	0.66	0.72
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	1.96	3.87	2.90
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	4.85	5.80	-3.51
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	14.0	10.49	9.21

The uncertainty budgets calculated for the analysis d-limonene, α-pinene, and 3-carene using the MS detector are higher than the target expanded uncertainty of 6%, indicating that this

method is not suitable for the analysis of these compounds. The large combined uncertainties are due to the large analytical bias using this detector.

10: Conclusion

The evaluation criteria for the validation of the analytical methods using GC-MS and GC-FID for the quantification of total terpenes in biomethane are summarised in Tables 15 and 16.

Table 15 – Summary of performance evaluation criteria for validation of analytical method for quantifying terpenes in biomethane using GC-FID. Criteria which have met the performance requirements are highlighted in green.

Criterion	Target value	d-limonene	α -pinene	3-carene
Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.01-10.0	0.066-3.280	0.067-3.367	0.063-3.123
R^2 over working range	> 0.995	0.999	0.999	0.998
LOD (nmol mol^{-1})	< 30	12	13	12
LOQ (nmol mol^{-1})	< 100	40	42	37
Trueness (%)	< 6.00	0.94	2.80	0.12
Repeatability u_r (%)	< 6.00	0.85	0.41	1.07
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	< 6.00	5.38	0.19	0.44
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	< 6.00	11.04*	5.67	2.32

The validation of the method for analysing terpenes in biomethane was performed according to the performance assessment protocol written in A2.1.4. The method described herein for the analysis of d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene in biomethane using the FID detector is therefore valid to the above-described acceptance criteria. As discussed in section 9, the large expanded uncertainty for d-limonene using FID can be improved by excluding outlying data from the reproducibility analysis, leading to an expanded uncertainty of 3.85% which is considered acceptable for this application.

Table 16 – Summary of performance evaluation criteria for validation of analytical method for quantifying terpenes in biomethane using GC-MS. Criteria which have met the performance requirements are highlighted in green.

Criterion	Target value	d-limonene	α -pinene	3-carene
Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.0 1- 10. 0	0.00 5- 3.28 0	0.006 - 3.367	0.00 5- 3.12 3
R^2 over working range	> 0.9 95	0.99 8	0.999	0.99 9
LOD (nmol mol^{-1})	< 30	7	8	12
LOQ (nmol mol^{-1})	< 10 0	24	27	24
Trueness (%)	< 6.0 0	4.85	5.80	- 3.51
Repeatability u_r (%)	< 6.0 0	0.44	0.66	0.72
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	< 6.0 0	1.96	3.87	2.90
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	< 6.0 0	10.4 9	14.00	9.22

The method described herein for the analysis of d-limonene, α -pinene, and 3-carene in biomethane using the MS detector is therefore valid to the above-described acceptance criteria. Due to the large trueness uncertainty of this method, the expanded uncertainties are demonstrated to be greater than the target value of 6%.

REPORT

A.2.2.6: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for 2 terpenes TD-GC/MS/FID using the static standards produced in A1.1.2.

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1. Introduction

The BiometCAP project has developed a performance assessment protocol (A2.1.4) for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. Here, this performance assessment protocol was validated using the method ISO 2620:2024 for alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene. The method is based on thermal desorption followed by gas chromatography with a mass spectrometer and a flame ionization detector (TD-GC/MS-FID). The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

2. Materials and methods

The TD-GC/MS-FID instrument was operated in electron impact mode with standard conditions, including an electron energy of 70 eV and a mass scan range from 29 to 300 amu. The analysis utilized a BPX5 column measuring 50 m x 32 mm ID x 1 µm with 5% phenylpolysilphenylene siloxane. Sorbent tubes underwent a two-step thermal desorption process using a Markes TD100 desorber by first heating the tubes to 275 °C for seven minutes to release the adsorbed species. These substances were then focused at -10 °C in a cold trap containing graphitized carbon before being rapidly heated to 300 °C for separation on the GC column. The column effluent was split for detection, with one stream passing through a flame ionization detector (FID) and the other through a mass spectrometer (MS).

A reference mixture produced by NPL in methane as part of activity A1.1.2 containing 3.32 ± 0.1 µmol/mol of alpha-pinene, 3.00 ± 0.1 µmol/mol of 3-carene and 3.18 ± 0.1 µmol/mol of R-limonene was used for the validation.

3. Validation

General overview

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Four steps with general procedure for determination of the performance characteristics.

Step	Phase	Description	Results
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1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	All terpenes, but the validation will be done for alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Only one gas mixture will be used: NPL mixture prepared as part of A1.1.2.
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Ca 3 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ per compound

The extent of the performance characteristic validation is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Extent of validation.

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Selectivity

Protocol: To perform the selectivity evaluation, use a reference material containing both the analyte of interest and other components that are expected to be present within the biomethane samples.

Here we used a reference biogas sample containing both the analyte of interest and other components. The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability to measure the analyte of interest in the sample where interferences have been introduced. The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest and the other components

present in the sample. Using GC parameters in this method, the following chromatogram was obtained for a biogas sample from a plant digesting food waste (figure 1).

Resolution was calculated according to this equation [1]:

$$\frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{\frac{1}{2}(W_1 + W_2)}$$

Where t_{R2} , t_{R1} are retention time for each peak and W_1 , W_2 are width of each peak. A resolution of 1.5 or more occurs when the signal returns to its baseline between two peaks, indicating good separation. Dimethyl-octadiene eluate close to alpha-pinene and calculation of the peak resolution gives a value of 1.1, signifying poor resolution. 1-Methyl-2-piperidinone eluate close to 3-carene with a peak resolution of 1.3, indicating a slight overlap between peaks. Beta-phellandrene and p-cymene eluate close to R-limonene but peaks are well separated with a resolution greater than 1.5.

Figure 1. Gas chromatogram of a biogas from a plant digesting food waste where Dimethyl-octadiene eluate close to alpha-pinene, 1-Methyl-2-piperidinone eluate close to 3-carene and R-limonene shows good separation.

Limit of detection and quantification

Protocol: the LOD and LOQ are calculated in one of two ways: via replicate measurements of blank samples, or via replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte. Here we used the second method.

The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for Alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene was calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. The LOD is determined for S/N = 3 and the LOQ for S/N = 10. The results are presented in Table 3. The results show that the method is highly sensitive and can be used to analyze samples with low amount fractions of terpenes.

Table 3. Calculated limits of detection and quantification for terpenes.

Compounds	Target amount ng	Noise	Signal	S/N at target amount	LOD ng (S/N = 3)	LOQ ng (S/N = 10)
Alpha-pinene MS	11.3	850	35900	42	0.80	2.7
3-carene MS	10.2	700	26400	38	0.81	2.7
R-limonene MS	10.8	600	25400	42	0.76	2.5
Alpha-pinene FID	11.3	100	17700	177	0.19	0.64
3-carene FID	10.2	100	15500	155	0.20	0.66
R-limonene FID	10.8	50	15400	308	0.11	0.35

Working range and linearity

Protocol: To assess the instrument working range:

- 1) Identify the **range of interest** (recommended to span $\pm 10\%$ of the expected calibration range) and measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across this range: 10 to 500 ng.
- 2) Plot response against amount fraction and visually examine plot to identify the approximate **linear range**.
- 3) To quantify linearity over the identified **linear range**, measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across the linear range.
- 4) Plot response (y axis) against amount fraction (x axis) and calculate appropriate regression statistics. Plot the residuals (difference in observed y value and predicted by the straight line fit). Random distribution around zero confirms linearity.

Alpha-pinene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of alpha-pinene. Results for alpha-pinene measured in the range 11 to 375 ng are shown in Figure 2. As illustrated in Figure 2, the correlation coefficient for alpha-pinene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 11 to 375 ng.

Figure 2. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 3).

Figure 3. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

3-carene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of 3-carene. Results for 3-carene measured in the range 10 to 339 ng are shown in Figure 4. As illustrated in Figure 4, the correlation coefficient for 3-carene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 10 to 339 ng.

Figure 4. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 5).

Figure 5. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

R-limonene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of R-limonene. Results for R-limonene measured in the range 11 to 360 ng are shown in Figure 6. As illustrated in Figure 6, the correlation coefficient for R-limonene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 11 to 360 ng.

Figure 6. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 7).

Figure 7. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

Trueness, Bias

Protocol, approach 1: **evaluation against a reference material:** compare mean measured value, with the reference value for the reference material. Calculate bias, relative bias, or the relative recovery (apparent recovery)

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are minimal. Thus, the biases are negligible, as shown in Tables 4, 5, and 6. This indicates that the instrument was pre-calibrated accurately, and no further correction is needed.

Table 4. Bias calculated for Alpha-pinene with FID.

Results μmol/mol	Expected results, μmol/mol	Bias	Relative Bias
18859	18771	88	0
19295	18771	524	3
19125	18771	354	2
19138	18771	367	2
18927	18771	156	2
	Mean	298	1.8

Table 5. Bias calculated for 3-carene with FID.

Results μmol/mol	Expected results, μmol/mol	Bias	Relative Bias
16945	16962	-17	0
17130	16962	168	1
17017	16962	55	0
16999	16962	37	0
16740	16962	-222	-1
	Mean	4	0

Table 6. Bias calculated for R-limonene with FID.

Results μmol/mol	Expected results, μmol/mol	Bias	Relative Bias
17907	17979	-72	0
18055	17979	76	0
17978	17979	-1	0
17902	17979	-77	0
17785	17979	-194	-1
	Mean	-54	-0.2

Precision

Protocol: **To evaluate repeatability** measure the analyte(s) of interest within a reference material at various concentrations spread across the working range using the same method. Obtain at least 10 replicate measurements and calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation.

Precision was assessed by measuring 13 duplicates of Alpha-pinene, 3-carene, and R-limonene at varying quantities using TD-GC-MS/FID on several days. Standard deviation, as

well as relative standard deviation, were determined and the pooled standard deviation was calculated. The results can be found in Table 7-12.

Table 7. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Alpha-pinene using TD-GC-FID

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	104	103	0.8	0.7
2 (240205)	144	143	0.5	0.3
3 (240205)	213	208	3.2	1.5
4 (240207)	23	24	0.2	0.9
5 (240207)	66	64	1.5	2.4
6 (240207)	138	134	3.2	2.4
7 (240207)	274	266	5.8	2.2
8 (240209)	200	204	2.8	1.4
9 (240209)	287	287	0.2	0.1
10(240209)	434	434	0.0	0.0
11(240209)	576	588	8.1	1.4
12(240219)	113	109	2.2	2.0
13(240219)	203	207	2.3	1.1
			sr%	1.7

Table 8. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Alpha-pinene using TD-GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	58	57	0.8	1.5
2 (240205)	80	79	0.5	0.6
3 (240205)	120	117	2.4	2.1
4 (240207)	11	11	0.1	0.9
5 (240207)	36	35	0.8	2.4
6 (240207)	78	74	2.7	3.6
7 (240207)	156	149	4.8	3.2
8 (240209)	107	110	1.9	1.8
9 (240209)	162	162	0.5	0.3
10(240209)	251	255	3.0	1.2
11(240209)	331	342	7.6	2.2
12(240219)	64	61	2.1	3.4
13(240219)	114	117	2.1	1.8
			sr%	2.1

Table 9. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 3-carene using TD-GC-FID

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	88	86	1.4	1.6
2 (240205)	122	121	0.8	0.7
3 (240205)	180	176	3.5	2.0
4 (240207)	18	17	0.1	0.7
5 (240207)	54	52	1.3	2.5
6 (240207)	115	111	2.8	2.5
7 (240207)	229	221	5.8	2.6
8 (240209)	164	167	2.1	1.3
9 (240209)	240	237	2.4	1.0
10(240209)	359	362	1.7	0.5
11(240209)	483	488	4.2	0.9
12(240219)	97	95	1.4	1.4
13(240219)	178	179	1.0	0.6
			sr%	1.9

Table 10. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 3-carene using TD-GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	39	38	1.0	2.5
2 (240205)	54	54	0.4	0.8
3 (240205)	82	78	2.6	3.2
4 (240207)	6	6	0.1	1.0
5 (240207)	23	22	0.2	0.9
6 (240207)	51	49	1.7	3.4
7 (240207)	105	101	3.3	3.2
8 (240209)	70	72	1.4	2.0
9 (240209)	110	108	1.0	0.9
10(240209)	171	173	1.7	2.0
11(240209)	228	233	3.7	1.6
12(240219)	44	42	1.0	2.4
13(240219)	81	82	0.6	0.7
			sr%	2.2

Table 11. Estimation of the intermediate precision for R-limonene using TD-GC-FID.

*Calculate without these values (considered as outliers).

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	84	83	0.9	1.1
2 (240205)	118	117	0.4	0.4
3 (240205)	173	169	2.8	1.6
4 (240207)	16	16	0.1	0.5
5 (240207)	50	49	0.7	1.5
6 (240207)	107	103	2.4	2.3
7 (240207)	214	206	6.1	2.9
8 (240209)*	148	165	11.9	7.6
9 (240209)*	221	259	27.3	11.4
10(240209)	362	339	16.6	4.7
11(240209)	453	466	8.9	1.9
12(240219)	102	100	1.0	1.0
13(240219)	188	189	0.6	0.3
			sr%	2.1

Table 12. Estimation of the intermediate precision for R-limonene using TD-GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	28	27	0.8	3.0
2 (240205)	40	40	0.0	0.0
3 (240205)	62	60	1.6	2.6
4 (240207)	4	4	0.0	0.6
5 (240207)	16	15	0.2	1.0
6 (240207)	36	35	1.3	3.6
7 (240207)	77	74	2.5	3.4
8 (240209)	49	51	0.8	1.6
9 (240209)	79	79	0.3	0.3
10(240209)	124	125	0.1	0.0
11(240209)	167	172	3.0	1.8
12(240219)	36	34	1.3	3.6
13(240219)	68	69	0.7	1.0
			sr%	2.4

Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) were calculated using the software MUKit. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable. The calculations show that measurement uncertainties are 9% and the method can therefore be considered reliable (Table 13).

Table 13. Within-laboratory reproducibility, method biases and expanded uncertainties from the TD-GC-MS/FID system for terpenes.

Compounds	$u(R_w)$ rel.	$u(\text{bias})$ rel.	$U = 2u_c$
Alpha-pinene	2.49 %	3.41 %	9 %
3-carene	2.62 %	3.31 %	9 %
R-limonene	2.76 %	3.12 %	9 %

4. Conclusions

The validation of the method ISO 2620:2024 for terpenes was performed for alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene according to the performance assessment protocol written in (A2.1.4). However, only one CRM was used compared to three recommended in the protocol for a linear regression, but the method had previously been validated using 5 different CRM.

ISO 2620:2024 is therefore found to be fit-for-purpose, reliable and highly sensitive. As the working range is at least 10 to 500 ng, it can be used to analyze samples with amount fractions of terpenes from 10 nmol/mol to 5 μ mol/mol (using volumes of 25 to 200 ml per tube).

5. References

[1] Shimadzu, <https://www.shimadzu.com/an/service-support/technical-support/analysis-basics/basic/resol-1.html>